

The Effect of Social Media Marketing on Purchase Intention Through Brand Awareness on Sociolla E-Commerce Users in Pekanbaru City

Kristina Permata Sari Sitorus

Universitas Riau, Pekanbaru

*Email : kristina.permata6116@student.unri.ac.id

Gatot Wijayanto

Magister of Management, Faculty of Economics and Business, Riau University

Email : gatotwijayanto@lecturer.unri.ac.id

Aida Nursanti

Magister of Management, Faculty of Economics and Business, Riau University

Email : aidanursanti1601@gmail.com

ARTICLE INFO :

Keywords :

Social Media Marketing;
Purchase Intention ;
Brand Awareness

Article History :

Received : 2024-03-26

Revised : 2024-05-02

Accepted : 2024-08-10

Online : 2024-09-10

ABSTRACT

This study aims to determine the effect of social media marketing on buying interest through brand awareness on sociolla e-commerce users in pekanbaru city. The sampling technique used purposive sampling with non-probability sampling. Data was obtained by distributing questionnaires to 120 respondents. The approach used in this research is quantitative and uses the SEM-PLS model and SmartPLS 4.0 software as a tool for this research. The results of this study indicate that: there is a positive and significant influence of social media marketing on brand awareness on Sociolla e-commerce users in Pekanbaru City, there is a positive and significant influence of brand awareness on buying interest in Sociolla e-commerce users in Pekanbaru City, there is a positive and significant influence of social media marketing on buying interest in Sociolla e-commerce users in Pekanbaru City, there is a positive and significant influence of social media marketing on buying interest through brand awareness on Sociolla e-commerce users in Pekanbaru City. For further researchers, it is hoped that this research will become a reference and analyze the time period and develop more research.

INTRODUCTION

The development of e-commerce in Indonesia has increased from year to year. Due to the increasing number of internet users in Indonesia. E-commerce has experienced impressive developments over the past few years due to technological innovations that led to changes in the company's marketing strategy. E-commerce considers the sales, trading, distribution, and marketing services of products and services that occur between organizations or individuals over the internet and company stakeholders. E-commerce emerged as a result of technological developments that led to a complete change in the company's marketing strategy (Burlacoiu, 2023).

Based on the 2019 Global Web Index data, Indonesia is the country with the highest adoption of e-commerce in the world. Buy online from 90% of internet users aged 16-64 years buy goods and services online (<https://www.cnnindonesia.com>). Data published on the beauty product business website sales increased in

each of these years with market revenue from sales of beauty and personal care products in Indonesia reaching almost 6.9 billion USD in 2019, indicating high public interest in the products (<https://talous.business.com>).

E-commerce has changed the way some people shop, from personal stores to online stores using computers or smartphones. The growth of e-commerce consumers in Indonesia is also predicted to continue to increase along with the increasing trend of digitalization. However, since the third quarter of 2022, several e-commerce companies in Indonesia have implemented mass layoffs to improve efficiency in accordance with their business development. When technology users find benefits from the technology they use, they tend to reuse it. Therefore, people are spoiled with increasingly sophisticated technology, making marketers also have to master it.

Information technology that is increasingly sophisticated, comes the activity of marketing products online, namely through social media. According to (Lia, 2022) Social media marketing can be interpreted as a marketing strategy that uses social media as its platform. According to Dave Chaffey (Fitria Rachmawati, 2018), digital marketing has the same meaning as electronic marketing (e-marketing). Digital Marketing is the application of digital technology that forms internet channels (Online Chanel) to the market (website, email, database, digital TV and the latest innovations. including blogs, podcast sources, and social networks) with marketing objectives to promote activities. Marketing is something important in business or business, marketing plays a big role in informing and delivering goods or services produced by companies to marketing consumers (Yacub and Mustajab, 2020).

Indonesia is one of the countries with the most internet users in the world. According to the We Are Social report, there were 204.7 million internet users in the country in January 2022. This number increased by 1.03 percent compared to the previous year. The government is expected to continue to support the expansion of internet coverage to all corners of the country. Because in this digital era, the internet really helps people to access information for education, business, and entertainment purposes.

Table 1. Preliminary survey

No.	Statement	Responses		Total Variety
		Yes	No	
1	Do you have buying interest in Sociolla e-commerce?	87,5% 35 people	12,5% 5 people	40 (100%)
2	Do you use one of e-commerce Sociolla’s social media?	65% 24 people	35% 16 people	40 (100%)
3	In your opinion, can the information shared on Sociolla e-commerce social media marketing influence your buying interest?	90,7% 36 people	9,3% 4 people	40 (100%)
4	In your opinion, can brand awareness of Sociolla e-commerce influence your buying interest?	88,4% 45 people	11,6% 5 people	40 (100%)
5	In your opinion, are there any differences in the influence between social media marketing and brand awareness on buying interest in Sociolla e-commerce in Pekanbaru City?	86% 34 people	14% 6 people	40 (100%)

Source : Data processed by researchers, 2023

The results of the pre-survey obtained results that as many as 90.7% or as many as 24 people said that the information shared by Sociolla e-commerce social media marketing could influence buying interest, but there were 9.3% or as many as 4 people saying that social media marketing could not influence buying interest. In addition, 88.4% or as many as 45 people said that Sociolla's brand awareness could influence buying interest and as many as 11.6% or as many as 5 people said that brand awareness could not influence buying interest. As many as 86% or as many as 34 people said that there was a difference in influence between social media marketing and brand awareness on Sociolla's e-commerce buying interest in Pekanbaru City.

Sociolla's repurchase interest is based on the number of customer visits to the site. Visits to the Sociolla website increased by 1.4 million to 4.8 million from 2018 to 2019 (Rizal, 2019). According to Rangkuti (2002) Brand awareness refers to the buyer's ability to recognize or remember that the brand is part of a particular product category (Yacub and Mustajab, 2020).

The various products sold and promoted by Sociolla make many people interested in buying. According to Ramadhan and Santosa (2017) purchase interest is having something in common with someone to use the products purchased by the company. In online purchase interest, it means the tendency of a consumer to buy products in online shopping (IWang, Li and Jiang, 2023).

LITERATURE RESEARCH

A. Consumer Behavior

Consumer behavior is defined as the behavior of consumers in looking to buy, use and consume products and services that are expected to satisfy their needs. Consumer behavior refers to the purchasing behavior of individuals and households who have just purchased goods or services for personal consumption. (Reska, Juliati Nst and Tambunan, 2023).

B. Marketing Communication

The definition of marketing communication according to (Nurdin Batjo, 2018) marketing communication is the communication of reciprocal information between producers and distributors or consumers who participate in marketing. The importance of marketing communication can be explained through the relationship between communication and marketing, because marketing communication is a combination of two studies, namely communication and marketing. In general, marketing communication refers to marketing activities that use communication methods to provide information to a large number of people, with the aim of increasing sales (profits) which is the goal of a company.

C. Social Media Marketing

According to (Anita, Sumarni Bayu, 2023) Social media marketing or social media marketing is a form of digital marketing that uses social platforms and networking sites that are useful for promoting an organization's products and services in a paid and unpaid manner. Social media marketing research conducted (Salamah, Nursal and Wulandari, 2023) has the following indicators: online communities, interaction, sharing of content, accessibility.

D. Purchase Intention

According to (Hartanto and Indriyani, 2021) purchase interest is consumer behavior that occurs in response to goods that show consumers' desire to buy. Purchase interest results from learning the thinking process that shapes perceptions. This buying interest creates a motivation that is continuously stored in the mind and becomes a very strong desire which in the end when consumers want to meet their needs, and realize what they want to do. The indicators in the purchase interest variable according to (Oktavia, 2023), namely: transactional interest, referential interest, preferential interest, exploratory interest.

E. Brand Awareness

According to (Febriani, N. S., & Dewi, 2018) says that brand awareness is a form of brand awareness related to the strength of the brand in people's memories, represented in people's minds, able to recognize

various brand elements (such as brand names, logos, symbols, characters, slogans and packaging) in different situations. The indicators in the brand awareness variable according to (Lestari and Nurhadi, 2023) are: Recall, recognition, purchase decision, consumption.

F. Conceptual Framework

Figure 1. Conceptual Framework

METHOD

This type of research uses a quantitative approach method to determine the effect of social media marketing on buying interest through brand awareness. This research was conducted in Pekanbaru City in 2023-2024. The population in this study were residents of Pekanbaru City who used Sociolla e-commerce and were interested in shopping at Sociolla e-commerce. The number of respondents in this study was determined as many as 120 respondents, sampling by non-probability sampling technique, namely by using purposive sampling. This data collection method was carried out by distributing questionnaires offline and online, the measurement scale used in this study was a Likert scale, using a scale of 1 to 5. The data analysis used in this study used Paetial Least Sqaure (PLS). PLS is a Structural Equation Model (SEM), this research was conducted with 3 stages, namely the measurement model (outer model), structural model (inner model) and hypothesis testing.

Table 2. Operational Definition of Variables

Variable	Operational Definition	Variable Indicator	Scale
Social Media Marketing	Marketing activities that involve many online communities, social networks, and others.	a. <i>Online communities</i> b. <i>Interaction</i> c. <i>Sharing of content</i> d. <i>Accessibility</i> (Salamah,Nursal and Wulandari,2023)	Ordinal Scale
Minat Beli	A feeling of attraction or desire for an object that is seen that arises from within or a person's attitude and causes a	a. Transactional interest. b. Referential interest. c. Preferential interest.	Ordinal Scale

Variable	Operational Definition	Variable Indicator	Scale
	series of positive reaction behaviors to make a purchase decision.	d. Explorative interest (Oktavia, 2023)	
Brand awareness	The ability of an individual to recognize and remember a product brand according to the product category.	a. <i>Recall.</i> b. <i>Recognition</i> c. <i>Purchase decision</i> d. <i>Consumption.</i> (Lestari and Nurhadi,2023)	Ordinal Scale

Source: Processed from various sources, 2023

For testing in this study, :

Outer Model

1. Convergent validity results

Convergent validity is measuring the validity of reflective indicators as a measure of latent variables which can be seen from the loading factor of each indicator variable and the AVE value of each variable or dimension.

2. Discriminant validity results

Discriminant validity involves comparing the square root of the average value of the variance extracted (AVE) of each construct with the correlation between other constructs in the model. This study shows that the loading factor value on the intended construct is greater than the loading factor on other constructs, so it is said that each indicator on the social media marketing variable, purchase intention and brand awareness is discriminantly valid.

3. Realibility validity results

This realibilitas test is a measuring tool to measure an indicator of a variable. The reliability test is carried out with two criteria, namely by means of Composite reliability and Cronbach alpha.

a. Composite reliability

The research instrument items that measure social media marketing variables, purchase intention and brand awareness in this study have a composite reliability value greater than 0.7.

b. Cronbach’s Alpha

Cronbach alpha is greater than 0.7 for all constructs. This shows that all instrument items are reliable in measuring their variables.

4. Coefficient of determination / R-Square (R²)

The coefficient of determination (R-Square) is a way to assess the extent to which an endogenous construct can be explained by an exogenous construct. The coefficient of determination (R-Square) must be between 0 and 1.

5. Q-Square predictive relevance (Q²)

Q-Square predictive relevance (Q²) is used to determine the degree of relationship between the independent variable and the dependent variable. The purpose of predictive relevance is to determine whether there is a good match between the independent variable and the dependent variable.

6. Model Fit

Model fit is a test conducted to see how well a model is studied. This test needs to be seen from the NFI (Normed Fit Index) results.

7. Hypotesist Test

The research hypothesis is carried out to test the truth in a statement and make a conclusion to accept or reject the statement.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 3. Respondents by age

No	Age	Frequency (People)	Percentage (%)
1	18-21 years old	42	35,0%
2	22-25 years old	35	29,2%
3	26-28 years old	23	19,2%
4	29-30 years old	20	16,6%
Amount		120	100,0%

Source : Appendix 4

In the age-based category, it can be seen that the number of Sociolla E-commerce users in the population in Pekanbaru city is dominated by ages between 18-21 years, totaling 42 people with a percentage of 35.0%. Then, followed by ages 22-25, which amounted to 35 people and had a percentage of 29.2%, the age group 26-28 years amounted to 23 people with a percentage of 19.2% and the age group 29-30 years amounted to 20 people with a percentage of 16.6%.

Table 4. Respondents based on district domicile

No	Sub-district domicile	Frequency (People)	Percentage (%)
1	Binawidya	20	16,7%
2	Bukit Raya	6	5,0%
3	Kulim	2	1,7%
4	Lima Puluh	5	4,2%
5	Marpoyan Damai	19	15,8%
6	Payung Sekaki	7	5,8%
7	Pekanbaru Kota	9	7,5%
8	Rumbai	6	5,0%
9	Rumbai Barat	5	4,2%
10	Rumbai Timur	3	2,5%
11	Sail	2	1,7%
12	Senapelan	10	8,3%
13	Sukajadi	7	5,8%
14	Tenayan Raya	5	4,2%
15	Tuah Madani	14	11,6%
Amount		120	100,0%

Source : Appendix 4

Based on the domicile of the sub-district, binawidya sub-district is dominated by 20 people and a percentage of 16.7%. Furthermore, bukit raya sub-district amounted to 6 people with a percentage of 5.0%. Kulim sub-district amounted to 2 people with a percentage of 1.7%. Kecamatan fifty amounted to 5 people with a percentage of 4.2%. Marpoyan damai sub-district amounted to 19 people with a percentage of 15.8%. Payung Sekaki sub-district had 7 people with a percentage of 5.8%. pekanbaru kota sub-district had 9 people with a percentage of 7.5%. Rumbai sub-district had 6 people with a percentage of 5.0%. West rumbai sub-district had 5 people with a percentage of 4.2%. East rumbai sub-district had 3 people with a percentage of 2.5%. Sail sub-district had 2 people with a percentage of 1.7%. Senapelan sub-district had 10 people with a

percentage of 8.3%. Sukajadi sub-district has 7 people with a percentage of 5.8%. Tenayan raya sub-district totaling 5 people with a percentage of 4.2%. Tuah Madani sub-district amounted to 14 people with a percentage of 11.6%.

Table 5. Respondents by gender

No	Gender	Frequency (People)	Percentage (%)
1	Man	29	24,2%
2	Women	91	75,8%
Amount		120	100,0%

Source : Appendix 4

Respondents based on gender stated that 91 respondents with female gender with a percentage of 75.8%. The number of male respondents totaled 29 people with a percentage of 24.2%. It is concluded that, Sociolla e-commerce users in Pekanbaru city with female respondents are more than male respondents.

Table 6. Respondents by type of employment

No	Type Of Work	Frequency (People)	Percentage (%)
1	Students	73	60,8%
2	PNS	4	3,3%
3	Private Employee	18	15,0%
4	Self-employed	21	17,6%
5	More	4	3,3%
Amount		120	100,0%

Source : Appendix 4

Based on the respondents in this study based on the type of work, the results are that respondents with the type of student / student work are more dominant, namely 73 people with a percentage of 60.8%. Respondents with the type of work of civil servants amounted to 4 people with a percentage of 3.3%. Respondents with the type of work of private employees amounted to 18 with a percentage of 15.0%. Respondents with the type of self-employed job totaled 21 with a percentage of 17.6%. Then respondents with other types of work amounted to 4 people with a percentage of 3.3%.

Table 7. Respondents by income

No	Income	Frequency (Orang)	Percent age (%)
1	≤ Rp 1.000.000,00	59	49,2%
2	≥ Rp 1.000.000,00 - Rp 2.000.000,00	10	8,3%
3	≥ Rp 2.000.000,00 - Rp 3.000.000,00	12	10,0%
4	≥ Rp 3.000.000,00 - Rp 4.000.000,00	26	21,7%
5	≥ Rp 4.000.000,00	13	10,8%
Amount		120	100,0%

Source : Appendix 4

Based on the table above, respondents in this study based on income have the highest income, namely income less than equal to Rp 1,000,000.00, totaling 10 people with a percentage of 49.2%. Respondents with income ≥ Rp 1,000,000.00 - Rp 2,000,000.00 amounted to 10 people with a percentage of

8.3%. Respondents with income ≥ Rp 2,000,000.00 - Rp 3,000,000.00 totaled 12 people with a percentage of 10.0%. Respondents with income ≥ Rp 3,000,000.00 - Rp 4,000,000.00 totaled 26 people with a percentage of 21.7%. Respondents with income ≥ Rp 4,000,000.00 amounted to 13 people with a percentage of 10.8%.

Table 8. Respondents based on the source of knowing E-commerce Sociolla

No	Where do you know about Sociolla E-Commerce?	Frequency (People)	Percentage (%)
1	Instagram	60	50,0%
2	Tiktok	60	50,0%
Amount		120	100,0%

Source : Appendix 4

The table above shows that respondents in this study knew E-commerce Sociolla from Instagram social media totaling 60 people with a percentage of 50% and respondents knew E-commerce Sociolla from Tiktok social media totaling 60 people with a percentage of 50%.

Table 9. Respondents based on reasons for having an interest in buying at Sociolla

No	What are the reasons you have an interest in buying at E-commerce Sociolla	Frequency (People)	Percentage (%)
1	Sells many famous cosmetic products	55	45,8%
2	Various payment methods	22	18,3%
3	Sociolla has many promos and vouchers	43	35,9%
Amount		120	100,0%

Source : Appendix 4

The table above shows that respondents have reasons for buying interest in E-commerce Sociolla, namely selling many well-known cosmetic products, totaling 55 people with a percentage of 45.8%. The reason respondents have an interest in buying at E-commerce Sociolla, namely various payment methods, totaling 22 people with a percentage of 18.3%. The reason respondents have an interest in buying at E-commerce Sociolla is that Sociolla has many promos and vouchers totaling 43 people with a percentage of 35.9%. So the highest respondent's reason for having an interest in buying at E-commerce Sociolla is selling many well-known cosmetic products.

1. Results of Convergent Validity Test of Research Variables

Table 10. Results of Convergent Validity Test of Research Variables

Variable	Indicator	Loading Factor	AVE
Social Media Marketing	X.1.1	0,884	0,670
	X.1.2	0,817	
	X.1.3	0,829	

	X.1.4	0,834	
	X.1.5	0,772	
	X.1.6	0,788	
	X.1.7	0,801	
	Y.1.1	0,857	
	Y.1.2	0,793	0,665
<i>Purchase Intention</i>	Y.1.3	0,801	
	Y.1.4	0,842	
	Y.1.5	0,823	
	Y.1.6	0,774	
	Z.1.1	0,854	
	Z.1.2	0,851	
<i>Brand Awareness</i>	Z.1.3	0,780	0,709
	Z.1.4	0,856	
	Z.1.5	0,866	

Source : Appendix 4

Indicators are said to be valid, if the outer loading coefficient is above 0.70. Based on the outer loading value, all items have a value above 0.70 and the AVE value in this study is above 0.5, so the convergent validity results for social media marketing variables, purchase intention and brand awareness are declared valid.

2.

Table 11. Fornell-Lacker Criterion Test Results

Variable	Social Media Marketing	Purchase Intention	Brand Awareness
<i>Social Media Marketing</i>	0,818		
<i>Purchase Intention</i>	0,761	0,816	
<i>Brand Awareness</i>	0,679	0,759	0,842

Source : Appendix 4

Another method for assessing discriminant validity is measurement by the Fornell-Larcker method which is done by comparing the square roots of the AVE with the latent vertical correlation. Discriminant validity is said to be good if the square root of the AVE along the diagonal line is greater than the correlation between one construct and another. From the table above, it can be seen that the square root value of AVE along the diagonal line is greater than the correlation between one construct and another, so it can be concluded that the construct has a good level of validity.

Table 12. Cross Loading Test Results

Statement	Social Media Marketing	Purchase Intention	Brand Awareness
X.1.1	0,884	0,680	0,632
X.1.2	0,817	0,677	0,584
X.1.3	0,829	0,628	0,580
X.1.4	0,834	0,583	0,534
X.1.5	0,772	0,656	0,598
X.1.6	0,788	0,540	0,430
X.1.7	0,801	0,565	0,494
Y.1.1	0,680	0,857	0,679
Y.1.2	0,564	0,793	0,564
Y.1.3	0,551	0,801	0,537

Y.1.4	0,702	0,842	0,735
Y.1.5	0,592	0,823	0,549
Y.1.6	0,607	0,774	0,615
Z.1.1	0,524	0,638	0,854
Z.1.2	0,571	0,672	0,851
Z.1.3	0,476	0,535	0,780
Z.1.4	0,595	0,652	0,856
Z.1.5	0,669	0,685	0,866

If the cross loading value of each indicator of the variable concerned is greater than the cross loading value of other variables, then the indicator is said to be valid. The recommended cross loading value is greater than 0.7 for each variable. The results of the cross loading value meet the standard, which is more than 0.7 and the discriminant validity test in this study is said to be valid.

Source : Appendix 4

Table 13. Cronbach Alpha and Composite Reliability Test Results

Variable	Cronbach's Alpha	Composite Reliability
<i>Social Media Marketing</i>	0,918	0,934
<i>Purchase Intention</i>	0,899	0,922
<i>Brand Awareness</i>	0,897	0,924

Source : Appendix 4

The reliability test is carried out by looking at the composite reliability and Cronbach's alpha values of the indicator block that measures the construct. The table above shows that the Cronbach's alpha value > 0.7 and composite reliability > 0.6 which indicates that all constructs in the estimated model meet the criteria (reliable).

Table 14. R-Square Test Results

Endogenous variable	R Square	R Square Adjusted
<i>Brand Awareness</i>	0,461	0,456
<i>Purchase Intention</i>	0,688	0,683

Source : Appendix 4

From the results above, it is known that the R Square brand awareness value is 0.461. This means that 46.1% brand awareness is influenced by social media marketing. Then the R Square value of purchase intention is 0.688. This means that 68.8% of buying interest is influenced by social media marketing and brand awareness.

Table 15. Predictive Relevance (Q²) Test Results

<i>Endogenous variable</i>	<i>Q² predict</i>
<i>Brand Awareness</i>	0,445
<i>Purchase Intention</i>	0,571

Source : Appendix 4

From the table above, it can be seen that each endogenous variable gets a Q2 value of 0.445 and 0.571 > 0. This means that this research model has a good observation value.

Table 16. Model Fit Test Results

<i>Index</i>	<i>Saturated model</i>
SRMR	0,068
d_ ULS	0,789
d_ G	0,485
Chi-square	306,077
NFI	0,821

Source : Appendix 4

From the above results, the SRMR value is 0.068 < 0.08 and the NFI value is 0.821 which is close to 1. It can be interpreted that the model assessment meets the fit model criteria.

Table 17. Research Hypothesis Testing Results

<i>Influence</i>	<i>Path Coefficient</i>	<i>T Statistics</i>	<i>P Values</i>
<i>Social Media Marketing -> Brand Awareness</i>	0,679	13,356	0,000
<i>Social Media Marketing -> Minat Beli</i>	0,455	6,310	0,000
<i>Brand Awareness -> Minat Beli</i>	0,451	6,604	0,000

Source : Appendix 4

1. Social Media Marketing -> Brand Awareness

Obtained a coefficient value of 0.679 with t-statistics of 13.356 and a P value of 0.000. These results show that the t statistic (13.356) is greater than the t table (1.65) or the P value (0.000) is smaller than 0.1. Thus, it can be interpreted that social media marketing has a positive and significant effect on brand awareness. Every increase in social media marketing by 1 unit, it will increase brand awareness by 0.679 and vice versa assuming other variables are constant.

2. Social Media Marketing -> Purchase intention

Obtained a coefficient value of 0.455 with t-statistics of 6.310 and a P value of 0.000. These results show that the t statistic (6.310) is greater than the t table (1.65) or the P value (0.000) is smaller than 0.1. Thus, it can be interpreted that social media marketing has a positive and significant effect on buying interest. Every increase in social media marketing by 1 unit, it will increase buying interest by 0.455 and vice versa assuming other variables are constant.

3. Brand Awareness -> Purchase interest

Obtained a coefficient value of 0.451 with t-statistics of 6.604 and a P value of 0.000. These results show that the t statistic (6.604) is greater than the t table (1.65) or the P value (0.000) is smaller than 0.1. Thus, it can be interpreted that brand awareness has a positive and significant effect on purchase intention. Every increase in brand awareness by 1 unit, it will increase purchase intention by 0.455 and vice versa assuming other variables are constant.

Table 18. Research Hypothesis Testing Results

Influence	Path Coefficient	T Statistics	P Values
Social Media Marketing -> Brand Awareness -> Purchase Intention	0,306	6,370	0,000

Source : Appendix 4

4. Social Media Marketing -> Brand Awareness -> Purchase Intention

Obtained a coefficient value of 0.306 with calculated t-statistics of 6.370 and a P value of 0.000. These results show that the t-statistic (6.370) is greater than the t table (1.65) or the P value (0.000) is smaller than 0.1. Thus, it can be interpreted that social media marketing has a positive and significant effect on purchase intention through brand awareness. Every increase in social media marketing mediated by brand awareness by 1 unit, it will increase buying interest by 0.306 and vice versa, assuming other variables are constant.

Figure 2 SmartPLS Structural Loading Factor Diagram

Figure 3 SmartPLS Structural Loading Factor Diagram

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This section will explain the results of the analysis in the research that has been conducted. There are four hypotheses in this study and have been tested using the Structural Equation Modeling - Partial Least Square method and using SmartPLS 4.0 software.

1. The Effect of Social Media Marketing on Brand Awareness

The results that have been obtained in this first hypothesis show that there is a positive and significant influence between social media marketing variables on brand awareness. These results are in accordance with the results of the path coefficient value obtained which is more than zero and the influence between variables can be stated as positive. The value of the T-Statistics test obtained is large. Thus, it can be interpreted that social media marketing has a positive and significant effect on brand awareness.

Based on the results obtained from distributing questionnaires to respondents, they stated that they joined the online community who were interested in Sociolla products, felt the influence of spreading positive content in the environment, easily accessing Sociolla information on social media and the cost of using Sociolla social media was affordable. The better in Sociolla's social media marketing, the better Sociolla's brand awareness / brand awareness and makes people always remember about Sociolla e-commerce.

This is in accordance with research conducted by (Yacub and Mustajab, 2020) which states the results that there is a positive and significant influence on social media marketing variables on brand awareness.

2. The Effect of Brand Awareness on Purchase Intention

The results that have been obtained in this second hypothesis show that there is a positive and significant influence between brand awareness on purchase intention. For the test results, the path coefficient value obtained on the brand awareness variable on purchase intention is greater than zero so that it is declared positive. Meanwhile, the T-Statistics test value obtained is large. Thus, it can be interpreted that brand awareness has a positive and significant effect on purchase intention.

Based on the results of distributing questionnaires to respondents, they stated that they remember Sociolla when discussing beauty products so that they are interested in buying and putting products in Sociolla in the shopping cart.

This is in accordance with research (Fadillah et al., 2017) which states the results that there is a positive and significant influence on brand awareness variables on purchase intention.

3. The Effect of Social Media Marketing on Purchase Intention

The results obtained in this third hypothesis show that there is a positive and significant influence between social media marketing on buying interest. For the results of the path coefficient test obtained on the

social media marketing variable on purchase intention is greater than zero and is declared positive. In the value of the T-Statistics test results, the value that has been obtained is greater. So with the value that has been obtained, it is stated that the relationship between social media marketing variables on buying interest is positive and significant.

This shows that Sociolla's social media marketing is good and makes respondents comfortable giving references to Sociolla products to others to be interested in buying and also recommending Sociolla products to people.

This is in accordance with the results of research (Arwachyntia and Sijabat, 2022) which states the results that there is a positive and significant influence on social media marketing variables on buying interest.

4. The effect of Social Media Marketing on Purchase Intention through Brand Awareness

The results obtained in this fourth hypothesis, there is a positive and significant effect of social media marketing on purchase intention through brand awareness and is evidenced by the T-Statistics value. The T-Statistics value obtained is greater, it means that the social media marketing variable on purchase intention through brand awareness is significant because the T-Statistics value is greater. With good social media marketing and brand awareness, it makes buying interest high in Sociolla e-commerce. The results of research by (Social and Marketing) found that there is a positive and significant influence of social media marketing on buying interest through brand awareness.

CONCLUSION

Based on the results of the research and discussion that has been carried out, the researcher draws conclusions about the effect of Social Media Marketing on Purchase Intention through Brand Awareness on Sociolla E-commerce Users in Pekanbaru City, the following conclusions from this study:

1. Social media marketing has a positive and significant effect on Brand Awareness for Sociolla E-commerce Users in Pekanbaru City. This means that with good and good social media marketing, namely the Sociolla introduces and posts interesting content and creates advertisements that attract many people to be interested in E-commerce Sociolla so that Sociolla's brand awareness is getting better.
2. Brand Awareness has a positive and significant effect on buying interest in Sociolla E-commerce Users in Pekanbaru City. This means that the better and better the brand awareness of Sociolla e-commerce, the higher the buying interest.
3. Social media marketing has a positive and significant effect on buying interest in Sociolla E-commerce Users in Pekanbaru City. That, the better the quality of Sociolla e-commerce social media marketing, the better and the higher the level of buying interest.
4. Social media marketing has a positive and significant effect on buying interest through Brand Awareness for Sociolla E-commerce Users in Pekanbaru City. This means that the higher the quality of Sociolla E-commerce social media marketing and brand awareness / brand awareness of Sociolla e-commerce, the higher the buying interest in shopping at Sociolla e-commerce.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

- Abdjul, F., Massie, J.D.. and Mandagie, Y. (2022) 'Pengaruh Content Marketing, Search Engine Optimization Dan Social Media Marketing Terhadap Keputusan Pembelian Mahasiswa Feb Unsrat Di E-Commerce Sociolla', *Jurnal EMBA : Jurnal Riset Ekonomi, Manajemen, Bisnis dan Akuntansi*, 10(3), p. 225. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.35794/emba.v10i3.41752>.
- Alehani, F.N., Wahid, A. and Abdul, B. (2023) 'Exploring Social Media and Organisational Sustainability Performance Goals : Themes , Functional Areas , and Practices Learning from the Preceding Decade'.
- Anggraini, T.R. (2022) 'Pengaruh Gaya Hidup dan Brand Awareness Terhadap Minat Beli Serta Dampaknya Pada Keputusan Pembelian Produk Emina (Studi pada Mahasiswa Administrasi Bisnis Angkatan 2018-2019 Universitas Mulawarman)', *CAPITAL: Jurnal Ekonomi dan Manajemen*, 5(2), p. 143. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.25273/capital.v5i2.12020>.
- Anita, Sumarni Bayu, S.S.M.A.C. (2023) *Entrepreneurship Communication*.

- Arwachyntia, S.S. and Sijabat, R. (2022) 'Analisa Pengaruh Social Media Influencer Dan Social Media Marketing Terhadap Brand Image Serta Dampaknya Pada Purchase Intention (Studi Kasus Pada Perawatan Wajah Pria)', *Jurnal Perilaku dan Strategi Bisnis, ejournal.mercubuana-yogya.ac.id.*, 10(1), pp. 1–20.
- Astri Rumondang, Acai Sudirman, S.S. et al. (2020) *Pemasaran Digital dan Perilaku Konsumen*. Edited by A. Riki. Available at: [https://ecampus.poltekkes-medan.ac.id/xmlui/bitstream/handle/123456789/6063/FullBook\(7\)_compressed.pdf?sequence=4](https://ecampus.poltekkes-medan.ac.id/xmlui/bitstream/handle/123456789/6063/FullBook(7)_compressed.pdf?sequence=4). Pemasaran Digital
- Atika Aini Nasution SE., M. and Bambang Sutejo, S.Kom., SE., M. (2022) *Manajemen Pemasaran*. Edited by C.M. Bincar Nasution, A.Pd. Available at: https://www.google.co.id/books/edition/Manajemen_Pemasaran/GcuWEAAAQBAJ?hl=ban&gbpv=1&dq=pemasaran+menurut+para+ahli&pg=PA47&printsec=frontcover.
- Burlacioiu, C. (2023) 'between 2019 and 2020'.
- Cahyadi, W. (2022) *Pemanfaatan Media terhadap Keberhasilan Wirausaha*. PT Inovasi Pratama Internasional. Available at: https://www.google.co.id/books/edition/Pemanfaatan_Media_terhadap_Keberhasilan/yHNIAAAQBAJ?hl=ban&gbpv=0.
- Christea, K. and Chairun Nisa, P. (2022) 'Pengaruh Advertising Disclosure Language terhadap Minat Beli Produk Beauty and Fashion di Instagram dengan Source Credibility sebagai Variabel Intervening', *Jurnal Manajemen dan Organisasi*, 13(1), pp. 12–22. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.29244/jmo.v13i1.37510>.
- Digdowniseiso, K., Lestari, R. and Safrina, D. (2022) 'Pengaruh Persepsi Harga Dan Promosi Terhadap Minat Beli Konsumen Melalui Brand Image Produk Kecantikan Di Aplikasi Sociolla', *Paper Knowledge . Toward a Media History of Documents*, 7(3).
- Dr. Nikolas F. Wuryaningrat, S.E., M.S. (2020) *Kemampuan Inovasi Industri Kreatif di Indonesia*. Edited by M. Prof. Dr. Paulus Kindangen SE., SU., M.A. Dr. Gris M. Sendow, S.E., and M.. Dr. Bode Lumanouw, S.E. Forum Pemuda Aswaja. Available at: [https://books.google.co.id/books?id=8AsNEAAAQBAJ&newbks=0&printsec=frontcover&pg=PA67&dq=evaluasi+model+struktural+\(inner+model\)&hl=ban&source=newbks_fb&redir_esc=y#v=onepage&q=evaluasi+model+struktural+\(inner+model\)&f=false](https://books.google.co.id/books?id=8AsNEAAAQBAJ&newbks=0&printsec=frontcover&pg=PA67&dq=evaluasi+model+struktural+(inner+model)&hl=ban&source=newbks_fb&redir_esc=y#v=onepage&q=evaluasi+model+struktural+(inner+model)&f=false).
- Ekasari, R. et al. (2023) *Komunikasi Bisnis (Pendekatan Praktis)*. Edited by H.F. Ningrum. Penerbit Media Sains indonesia. Available at: https://www.google.co.id/books/edition/Komunikasi_Bisnis_Pendekatan_Praktis/Dju9EAAAQBAJ?hl=ban&gbpv=1&dq=kesadaran+merek+aaker+dalam+sihaan&pg=PA38&printsec=frontcover.
- Ernestivita, G., Budiyanto and Suhermin (2023) *Seni Digital Marketing untuk Meningkatkan Pembelian Impulsif dan Compulsif*. Edited by R. R.Rerung. Penerbit Media Sains indonesia. Available at: https://www.google.co.id/books/edition/Seni_Digital_Marketing_untuk_Meningkatka/NyiuEAAAQBAJ?hl=ban&gbpv=1&dq=menurut+harir+2014+jika+ukuran+sampel&pg=PA112&printsec=frontcover.
- Fadillah, I. et al. (2017) 'Prosiding Seminar Nasional Ekonomi Dan Bisnis 1 Fakultas Ekonomi dan Bisnis Universitas Muhammadiyah Surabaya Pengaruh Brand Awareness , Kualitas Produk , Dan Word Of Mouth (WOM) Terhadap Minat Beli Skin Care Lokal Di Sociolla Prosiding Seminar Nasional', *Prosiding Seminar Nasional Ekonomi Dan Bisnis 1 Fakultas Ekonomi dan Bisnis Universitas Muhammadiyah Surabaya*, pp. 187–192.
- Fauziah Septiani, S.E., M.. (2022) *Dasar Dasar Pemasaran Digital*.
- Febriani, N. S., & Dewi, W.W.A. (2018) 'Teori dan Praktis Riset Komunikasi Pemasaran Terpadu'.
- Firmansyah, M.A. (2020) 'Pemasaran Produk Dan Merek (Planning & Strategy)', *Jurnal Ilmu Manajemen* [Preprint].
- Fitria, M, N.R. and Arumsari, I. (2021) *Manajemen Data Untuk Survei Gizi*. Edited by R. R.Rerung. Penerbit Media Sains Indonesia. Available at: https://books.google.co.id/books?id=oddVEAAAQBAJ&newbks=0&printsec=frontcover&pg=PA144&dq=definisi+uji+realibilitas&hl=ban&source=newbks_fb&redir_esc=y#v=onepage&q=definisi+uji+realibilitas&f=false.
- Hamali, S. et al. (2023) *Metodologi Penelitian Manajemen : Pedoman Praktis Untuk Penelitian & Penulisan*

- Karya Ilmiah Ilmu Manajemen*. Edited by E.& Sepriano. PT. Sonpedia Publishing Indonesia. Available at: https://www.google.co.id/books/edition/Metodologi_Penelitian_Manajemen_Pedoman/mXPkEAAAQBAJ?hl=ban&gbpv=1.
- Hartanto, B. and Indriyani, L. (2021) *Minat beli di Marketplace Shopee*. PT Inovasi Pratama Internasional. Available at: https://www.google.co.id/books/edition/Minat_Beli_di_Marketplace_Shopee/iP56EAAAQBAJ?hl=ban&gbpv=0.
- Hartanto, B. and Indriyani, L. *Minat Beli Di Marketplace Shopee*. PT. Inovasi Pratama Internasional. Available at: https://www.google.co.id/books/edition/Minat_Beli_di_Marketplace_Shopee/iP56EAAAQBAJ?hl=ban&gbpv=0.
- IWang, X., Li, G. and Jiang, R. (2023) 'Research on Purchase Intention of E-Commerce Poverty Alleviation Products Based on Perceived Justice Perspective', *Sustainability*, 15(3), p. 2252. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.3390/su15032252>.
- Kambolong, M., Nurjannah and Ambarwati, L. (2021) *Metode Riset Dan Analisis Saluran Distribusi*. Edited by T.Q. Media. Available at: https://books.google.co.id/books?id=46tXEAAAQBAJ&newbks=0&printsec=frontcover&pg=PA80&dq=faktor+faktor+yang+mmpengaruh+minat+beli+ecommerce&hl=ban&source=newbks_fb&redir_esc=y#v=onepage&q=faktor faktor yang mmpengaruh minat beli ecommerce&f=false.
- Khalifah, A.R., Triwardhani, D. and Syarief, N. (2021) 'Keputusan Penggunaan Bni Mobile (Studi Kasus Pada Pengguna BNI Mobile Di Jakarta)', *Konferensi Riset Nasional Ekonomi, Manajemen, dan Akuntansi*, 2, pp. 962–980.
- Latan, G.& (2015).
- Lestari, V.W. and Nurhadi (2023) 'Pengaruh Brand Ambassador dan Tagline Terhadap Brand Awareness Shopee Indonesia di Surabaya', *Jurnal Administrasi Bisnis*, 13(1), pp. 9–16. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.35797/jab.13.1.9-16>.
- Lia, S. (2022) 'No Title העינים לנגד מה שבאמת את מה קשה לראות את מה', *הארץ*, 4(8.5.2017), pp. 2003–2005. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.31539/jomb.v4i2.4500>.
- Mohamad Basuni et al. (2023) 'Analisis Pengaruh Perilaku Konsumen Dalam Pengambilan Keputusan Pembelian Online Masyarakat Kabupaten Brebes Pada E-Commerce Shoppe', *E-Bisnis : Jurnal Ilmiah Ekonomi dan Bisnis*, 16(1), pp. 10–18. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.51903/e-bisnis.v16i1.873>.
- Musyaffi, A.M., Khairunnisa, H. and Respati, D.K. (2021) *Konsep Dasar Structural Equation Model-Partial Least Square(Sem-Pls) Menggunakan Smart Pls*.
- Nasrullah 'Media Sosial: Perspektif Komunikasi, Budaya, dan Sosioteknologi.', 2016 [Preprint].
- Nurdin Batjo, S.P.M.M. sumber manusia (2018) 'Nurdin Batjo', 1(2).
- Oktavia, C. (2023) 'Pengaruh Brand Ambassador Song Jong Ki Dan Brand Image Scarlett Whitening Terhadap Minat Beli Konsumen', *Communique*, 5(2), pp. 1–23.
- Pelanggan, P.K. et al. (2023) 'Niat Beli Produk Skincare Melalui Pemasaran Viral Sebagai', 10(1), pp. 53–65.
- Penitasari, N. (2017) 'Pengaruh Harga dan Kualitas Produk Terhadap Minat Beli Abon Lele'.
- Prasetyo, F.I., Budiyanto, M.A. and Reformasi, E. (2022) 'Pengaruh Brand Awareness, Brand Loyalty dan Brand Image Terhadap Minat Beli Produk Online di Marketplace Tokopedia (Study Kasus Konsumen Tokopedia Jabodetabek)', *JUEB : Jurnal Ekonomi dan Bisnis*, 1(3), pp. 58–67. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.55784/jueb.v1i3.261>.
- Prawiyogi, A.G. et al. (2021) 'Penggunaan Media Big Book untuk Menumbuhkan Minat Membaca di Sekolah Dasar', *Jurnal Basicedu*, 5(1), pp. 446–452. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.31004/basicedu.v5i1.787>.
- Rahmadani, E. et al. (2023) *Statistika Pendidikan*. Edited by A. Yanto. PT Global Eksekutif Teknologi. Available at: https://books.google.co.id/books?id=c6y5EAAAQBAJ&newbks=0&printsec=frontcover&pg=PA49&dq=sumber+jenis+data+sugiyono+2019&hl=ban&source=newbks_fb&redir_esc=y#v=onepage&q=sumber jenis data sugiyono 2019&f=false.
- Rahmawati (2022) *Apa Saja Variabel Penelitian Dalam Bidang Marketing ???* Edited by M.S. i. Prof. Dr. Sri Widiastuti, S.E., M.M. Penerbit Deepublish. Available at: <https://books.google.co.id/books?id=->

- 3KcEAAAQBAJ&newbks=0&printsec=frontcover&pg=SL9-PA4&dq=definisi+operasional+variabel+adalah&hl=ban&source=newbks_fb&redir_esc=y#v=onepage&q=definisi+operasional+variabel+adalah&f=false.
- Ramadhanti, P.S., Arifin, H. and Hidayat, R.M. (2021) 'Pengaruh Potongan Harga, E-Word of Mouth, Dan Kepercayaan Terhadap Minat Beli Pada Sociolla Di Banjarmasin', *Smart Business Journal*, 2(1), pp. 1–11.
- Reska, A., Juliati Nst, Y.S. and Tambunan, K. (2023) 'Faktor-Faktor yang Mempengaruhi Keputusan Konsumen Membeli Produk Takaful Dana Pendidikan pada PT Takaful Keluarga Cabang Medan', *Jurnal Ilmu Komputer, Ekonomi dan Manajemen (JIKEM)*, 3(1), pp. 951–985.
- Salamah, M., Nursal, M.F. and Wulandari, D.S. (2023) 'Peran Social Media Marketing, Brand Image Dan Kualitas Produk Terhadap Keputusan Pembelian Pada Produk Kosmetik Madame Gie Di Kab. Bekasi', *Jurnal Economina*, 2(10), pp. 2686–2703. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.55681/economina.v2i10.894>.
- 'Priatni, S.B., Hutriana, T., dan Hindarwati, E. N., Pengaruh Social Media Marketing... ISSN: 2460 - 8114 (print) 2656 - 6168 (online)', 8114.
- Sovia, A., Shalsa, P. and Putri, Y. (2023) 'Analisis Kualitas Pelayanan Paket Express Terhadap Kepuasan Pelanggan Dengan Metode Structural Equation Modeling (Sem) (Studi Kasus : PT Amaly Mitraabadi Sulawesi) Email : aditiasovia@ulbi.ac.id PT Amaly MitraAbadi Sulawesi is a private company in the', 13(September), pp. 14–21.
- Sugiyono (2018) 'Metode Penelitian Kuantitatif'.
- Upadana, W. K., & Pramudana, A.S. (2020) 'Brand Awareness Memediasi Pengaruh Social Media Marketing terhadap Keputusan Pembelian.'
- Utami, P.P., Wilona, K. and Tabitha, C. (2022) 'Pengaruh Social Media Marketing Terhadap Ekuitas Merek E-Commerce Sociolla', *Jurnal Ilmu Pengetahuan Sosial*, 9(No 1), pp. 223–238. Available at: <http://jurnal.um-tapsel.ac.id/index.php/nusantara/index>.
- Wangsajaya, Y. et al. (2023) *Monograf Model Pengukuran Kualitas Layanan Publik Dengan Indikator Presisi Polri Berbasis Kecerdasan Buatan*. Edited by F. Sofiani. Available at: https://www.google.co.id/books/edition/Monograf_Model_Pengukuran_Kualitas_Layan/ibbYEAAAQBAJ?hl=ban&gbpv=1.
- Whang, J. Bin et al. (2021) 'The effect of Augmented Reality on purchase intention of beauty products: The roles of consumers' control', *Journal of Business Research*, 133(November 2019), pp. 275–284. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jbusres.2021.04.057>.
- Yacub, R. and Mustajab, W. (2020) 'Analisis Pengaruh Pemasaran Digital (Digital Marketing) Terhadap Brand Awareness Pada E-commerce', *Jurnal Manajerial*, 19(2), pp. 198–209. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.17509/manajerial.v19i2.24275>.

